

Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms

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To cite this article: Gregory K. Tharp (28 May 2025): Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms, Technical Services Quarterly, DOI: [10.1080/07317131.2025.2512289](https://doi.org/10.1080/07317131.2025.2512289)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317131.2025.2512289>

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Published online: 28 May 2025.

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Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms

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Cataloging psychological materials is unique. The Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms is part of the American Psychological Association (APA) website (<https://www.apa.org/>). This thesaurus is a controlled subject thesaurus on the field of psychology and contains universally accepted standard psychology terms for subsequent retrieval for searching and browsing. There are several separate headings: What's new in the Winter 2025 update, Sample of new terms added, Thesaurus features, and Contact us. To the right of these headings, there are related resources, such as Guide to the Fields in APA Database Records, which contain many useful tools for catalogers.

The What's new in the Winter 2025 update heading offers a link to a Portable Document Format (PDF) document titled Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms 2025 update which contains a listing of Examples of New Terms, New Postable Terms, Nonpostable Terms and Their Postable Counterparts, Edited Postable Terms, Term Changing From Nonpostable to Postable Status, Nonpostable Terms Changing Their Postable Counterpart, Deleted Nonpostable Term, and Scope Note Revisions. While this update does not provide definitions, the listing of terms does help catalogers seeking to catalog items that discuss such emerging topics as "Machine Ethics." As psychological literature most often appears in medical and health sciences libraries, the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms Winter 2025 update may be most relevant to catalogers and others working in medical and health sciences libraries who are likely to encounter psychological materials in their collection(s).

The Sample of new terms added heading also does not provide any definitions; however, it also helps catalogers seeking to catalog items that discuss such topics as "Ethics." This heading appears to be redundant with the What's new in the Winter 2025 update heading which diminishes its importance to catalogers and other library professionals using the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms.

The Thesaurus features heading defines terms including index terms as well as explains why a controlled vocabulary is important for searching. Understanding terms and index terms used in this thesaurus helps librarians understand why it is helpful to access psychological material(s) in their collection(s). Also, by examining the link to various database vendors for the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms, users can select a database vendor that is best for their collection(s) and user(s). The drawback of using a database vendor, especially for small to medium sized libraries and medical facilities, is that it is often expensive to purchase databases. For that reason, many catalogers and other library professionals may wonder if the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms would be able to be accessed using a free search bar like the Library of Congress subject headings in the future.

The Contact us heading allows anyone to suggest new terms and provides contact information which is helpful if additional psychological terms pertinent to the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms are in other databases. This heading

is a useful tool for catalogers and others in that their collection(s) may contain psychological term(s) not contained in the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms. The complete nature of all the headings within the Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms website makes the website seem complete and should be utilized by catalogers and other library professionals working with health sciences or medical library collections. The Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms is ranked 4 out of 5 due to the comprehensive nature of the website and difficulty of the navigation of the website.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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<https://doi.org/10.1080/07317131.2025.2512289>

